

Supplementary Material

**Influence of pH and NaCl on the rejection of glycine and triglycine in
binary solutions for desalination with diananofiltration**

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Figure S1

(A)

(B)

(C)

Fig. S1 - Glycine rejection in single solute solutions for the Desal 5DK membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S2

Fig. S2 - Glycine rejection in single solute solutions for the MPF-36 membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S3

Fig. S3 - Triglycine rejection in single solute solutions for the MPF-36 membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S4

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure S4 (continued)

Figure S4 (continued)

Fig. S4 - Glycine and NaCl rejections in binary solutions for the Desal 5DK membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S5

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure S5 (continued)

Fig. S5 - Glycine and NaCl rejections in binary solutions for the MPF-36 membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S6

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure S6 (continued)

(D)

(E)

Fig. S6 - Triglycine and NaCl rejections in binary solutions for the Desal 5DK membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.

Figure S7

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure S7 (continued)

(D)

(E)

(F)

Fig. S7 - Triglycine and NaCl rejections in binary solutions for the MPF-36 membrane as a function of the permeate flux and feed pH. Symbols represent the experimental data and lines the fitted data.